

**THEME: GOTHIC CLASSICS IN THE WORKS AND POETRY OF
EDGAR ALLAN POE**

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Annotation: There is a strong chance that you will have heard the name, Edgar Allan Poe, however, not everyone has read his work or understands his lasting impact, so if you're new to Poe or classic horror, allow me to help you explore the shadows of the genre and get to know its icons. Just like any good story, let's start at the very beginning, with the birth of Gothic Literature. Gothic Literature is the strange and awkward love child of the Romantic movement, born in the late 18th century. The genre has captivated readers in the centuries since its conception with its moody, darkly mysterious, and often chilling tales. In its black heart, this literary tradition harbors a deep fascination with the macabre.

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The gothic short stories and poems of Edgar Allan Poe are so outstanding that they are still being read today. He only lived for forty years yet made such a huge impact on literature. Poe tells Thomas W. Fredrick in a letter, why he became a writer. Depend upon it, after all, Thomas, Literature is the most noble of professions. In fact, it is about the only one fit for a man. For my own part, there is] no seducing me from the path. (Edgar Allan Poe's Life, intro page) The word that best describes the life and works of Edgar Allan Poe would have to be mystery.

Not only is it seen in his literary works, but in his life as well. Shortly after, his mother died of tuberculosis, the two children were all alone. In 1811, at the age of two, Poe was taken in by John and Frances Allan. Mr. Allan Refused to adopt Edgar but said he could stay with them. Rosalie was taken by another family. Poe lived in Richmond until he was six years old, then the Allans and Poe moved to Scotland. Poe attended school at Irvine Grammar School and for several years at Manor House School in Stoke Newington. (The Manor may have been reproduced in some of the darkly romantic houses in Poe's stories).

When Edgar was eleven the Allan's returned to Richmond. There he went to school at an English and Classical School attended by the more wealthy children. At this time, Edgar began to notice how different he was and began to feel

bitterness towards his mother and Mr. Allan. He expressed his feelings at age sixteen, when he began to write poems and short stories. He became very arrogant and didn't get along with anyone. When Edgar was seventeen years old, Mr. Allan sent him to the U. of Virginia in Charlottesville. In 1825, Edgar secretly engaged to Sarah Elmira Royster, who was only sixteen years old. At college, Edgar continuously drank, gambled, and fought. He began to drink and gamble so much, that he fell into debt so far that he couldn't pay his losses. Mr. Allan could no longer tolerate Poe's behavior so he withdrew him from school and put him to work at his counting house all within one year.

Edgar Allan Poe is most commonly known for his dark and mysterious poetry. His poems often explore the darkness of the human soul, and the macabre aspects of life. Many of his poems contain Gothic elements, such as ghosts, death, and decay. In addition to his poetry, Edgar Allan Poe also wrote short stories and novels that are often classified as Gothic as well. Some of his most famous Gothic works include *The Fall of the House of Usher*, *The Masque of the Red Death*, and *The Raven*. Despite his dark subject matter, Edgar Allan Poe's writing is extremely poetic and beautiful. He has been credited with changing the course of American literature, and is considered to be one of its greatest authors. Even today, his writings are still widely read and studied in schools. Edgar Allan Poe's influence can be seen in many modern authors, such as Stephen King and Anne Rice. In fact, King has said that —Poe is the father of us all. Thanks to Edgar Allan Poe, the Gothic genre is one of the most popular and enduring in all of literature. Edgar Allan Poe may be described as a gothic writer because of his preference for medieval locales, gloomy ambiences, and inexplicable and violent events. Poe was a very talented writer with a strong imagination.

Along with his enormous writing skill and vivid imagination; Poe had an apparently limitless vocabulary. He mostly composed poems and tales about dark and terror-inducing themes. *The Raven* is one of the most well-known poems written by Edgar Allan Poe to the English language. He also released one novel in addition to the many journals he contributed to. Gothic elements in Edgar Allan Poe's writing can be seen in the use of medieval settings, murky atmospheres, and mysterious and violent incidents. One of the reasons Edgar Allan Poe is considered a Gothic writer is because of his use of medieval settings in his works. Many of his poems take place in castles or abbeys, and his tales often have Gothic villains who wear monk's robes or dusty old armor. In —*The Masque of the Red Death*||, for example, Prince Prospero holds a masked ball in

an effort to forget the plague that is ravaging his land. But even in this setting of gaiety and revelry, death manages to make an appearance. A sinister figure dressed all in red arrives at the castle and begins killing all of the guests. Poe creates a feeling of unease in his reader by using a setting that is often associated with safety and security, but then introducing an element of danger. Another Gothic element that can be found in Edgar Allan Poe's writing is the use of murky atmospheres.

The works of Edgar Allan Poe continue to stand out in our literature through their gloomy settings and unusual characters and events. In many of his poems, Edgar Allan Poe placed the people or situations in somewhat medieval locales. His utilization of unique locations stands out particularly in *Ulalume*, which is one of world literature's most well-known poems. The narrator asks a raven flying into his chamber if he will ever see his lost love again in *The Raven*, the poet grieving the death of his lover Lenore in a chamber. Edgar Allan Poe's choice of a chamber as the setting for this poem creates an intimate feeling, which is a common element in gothic literature. Edgar Allan Poe also commonly wrote about death and decay, which are other elements of gothic literature. In his poem *The Bells*, Edgar Allan Poe writes about the sound of bells and how they can bring both happiness and sorrow. Edgar Allan Poe's writing style often times included dark and mysterious elements that were intriguing to his readers. His works were often associated with the genre because of these characteristics. Edgar Allan Poe's poems *The Raven* and *The Bells* are both excellent examples of his gothic style. In *The Raven*, Edgar Allan Poe creates a dark and depressing atmosphere through the use of death and loss. The poem is about a man who is grieving the death of his lover, Lenore. The poem is set in a chamber, which creates an intimate feeling. Edgar Allan Poe also uses sound words in *The Bells*, which create a haunting effect. These gothic elements make Edgar Allan Poe's writings unique and interesting to read even today.

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